

1 **Novel mechanisms of host microbe interactions for attaching/effacing bacteria.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
Enterohemorrhagic E. Coli (EHEC) are attaching/effacing bacteria that use aggressive, active mechanisms to establish infection that are highly colitogenic. We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in human Caco-2 cells following *in vitro* infection with EHEC. We describe here core components of the EHEC gene signature in human cells. The changes associated with infection Enterohemorrhagic E. Coli include changes in cellular identity marked by induction of *MAFF* and activation of the TCDD inducible poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase, *TIPARP*. EHEC infection in human colorectal cells resulted in activation of innate immune sensor *cGAS*.

12 Citations

13 1. Reilly, A., 1998. Prevention and control of enterohaemorrhagic Escherichia coli (EHEC) infections: memorandum from a WHO meeting. WHO Consultation on Prevention and Control of Enterohaemorrhagic Escherichia coli (EHEC) Infections. Bulletin of the World Health Organization, 76(3), p.245.

15 2. Pifer, R., Russell, R.M., Kumar, A., Curtis, M.M. and Sperandio, V., 2018. Redox, amino acid, and fatty acid metabolism intersect with bacterial virulence in the gut. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 115(45), pp.E10712-E10719.

17 3. Yang, W., Sun, H., Yan, J., Kang, C., Wu, J. and Yang, B., 2023. Enterohemorrhagic Escherichia coli senses microbiota-derived nicotinamide to increase its virulence and colonization in the large intestine. Cell Reports, 42(6).

19 4. Goldwater, P.N. and Bettelheim, K.A., 2012. Treatment of enterohemorrhagic Escherichia coli (EHEC) infection and hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS). BMC medicine, 10(1), p.12.

21 GSE255129